

Oxidation of 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazole by sodium periodate : a kinetic study

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Kinetics of oxidation of a few 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles by sodium periodate in aqueous acetic acid-HClO₄ medium have been studied. The reaction follows a first order rate each with respect to oxidant and substrate concentration. A suitable mechanism and rate expression pertinent to the observed data are suggested.

The synthesis of the oxadiazole ring is quite easily achieved from semicarbazide hydrochloride. This involves the introduction of a second carbon atom to the semicarbazide vide a cyclizing agent. The other route employs a 1,3,4-oxadiazole ring with a substituent as halogen atom or an alkyl or sulfonyl group, which, can be displaced by NH or an amine. Less common yet sometimes more useful are the methods by which the amino group is introduced with the cyclizing agent without the intermediate formation of a semicarbazide¹.

The oxidation of 2-aminooxadiazoles with various oxidizing agents is well documented in the literature. It leads to various types of products not necessarily affecting the amino group. However, the kinetics of such type of reactions are not reported in most of the cases. Thus, we report herein the synthesis and oxidation of some 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles with sodium periodate in aqueous acetic acid-HClO₄ medium.

Results and Discussion

2-Amino-oxadiazoles was synthesized from semicarbazide hydrochloride and aromatic carboxylic acids using concentrated sulfuric acid as the cyclizing agent similar to the synthesis of thiadiazoles². The kinetic data (Table 1) of the oxidation of 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles by sodium periodate in aqueous acetic acid medium in the presence of perchloric acid at 35° reveals the following observations : (i) the reaction follows a pseudo-first order change with rate constant $k_{1\text{obs}}$ with respect to the disappearing periodate concentration, (ii) it follows a first order rate dependence with respect to substrate concentration, (iii) in the higher [H⁺] range (0.075–0.2 M), $k_{1\text{obs}}$ is nearly independent of the change in [H⁺], (iv) $k_{1\text{obs}}$ is independent of the added electrolyte [KCl] and dielectric constant of the medium (i.e. a mixture of water-acetic acid in the range of 90–10% to

70–30%) and (v) the net Arrhenius parameters evaluated at 35° are $\Delta E = -5.0 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta H = -374.0 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S = -27.3 \text{ e.u.}$ and $\log A = 2.71$.

Oxidant species : Different species of periodic acid are known³ to exist in acidic medium, such as IO₄⁻, HIO₄ and H₂IO₄⁺; the most abundant species under the present experimental conditions appears to be HIO₄.

As observed, at higher concentrations of HClO₄ used,

Table 1. Pseudo-first order rate constant in the oxidation of 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazole by acid periodate

[IO ₄ ⁻] = 5 × 10 ⁻⁴ M	[S]	[H ⁺]	AcOH*	Temp.	KCl	k _{1obs}
	M	M	% (v/v)	°C	M	
	0.0100	0.050	20	35	0	2.77
	0.0025	0.050	20	35	0	0.94
	0.0050	0.050	20	35	0	1.60
	0.0075	0.050	20	35	0	2.11
	0.0200	0.050	20	35	0	8.80
	0.0100	0.075	20	35	0	2.07
	0.0100	0.100	20	35	0	2.01
	0.0100	0.200	20	35	0	2.00
	0.0100	0.050	10	35	0	2.58
	0.0100	0.050	30	35	0	2.57
	0.0100	0.050	20	25	0	0.88
	0.0100	0.050	20	30	0	1.77
	0.0100	0.050	20	40	0	2.93
	0.0100	0.050	20	35	0.005	2.77
	0.0100	0.050	20	35	0.010	2.77
	0.0100	0.050	20	35	0.020	2.77

*Water-acetic acid solvent mixture.

there is insignificant effect on the rate. At higher concentration (0.075–0.2 M) periodate ion exists itself as periodic acid, which is the oxidizing species, whereas at lower concentrations, it takes an external H⁺ ion to form the required oxidizing species. The small change in rate constant from 2.77 to 2.07 observed, when the acid concentration changes from 0.05 to 0.075, can be attributed due to participation of the free amine to form the corresponding anilinium ion.

Further, as a matter of fact, unsubstituted oxadiazoles bear two-reaction sites, viz. at 2-position and 5-position, among which the former is more reactive than the latter. However, when 2-position is occupied by some groups (inert towards oxidation or substitution) then the attacking agent is oriented to 5-position. Also, in normal course of reaction, substitution reaction precedes over oxidation when the attacking agent is a halogen carrier. Further, when both the positions are occupied and there is a group at 2-position, which can be oxidizable, then oxidation precedes over substitution. In the present situation 2-amino-5-aryloxadiazoles can conveniently be oxidized by periodate in acid medium. Periodate oxidizes the amino functionality to a reactive nitrene intermediate, which then dimerizes to form the product in subsequent steps (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Thus, we propose a generalized scheme for the reaction of periodate with 2-amino-5-aryloxadiazole in acid medium along with the rate expression as given below :

A rate law that can be derived for the above sequence is as follows :

$$\frac{-d[\text{IO}_4^-]/dt}{[\text{IO}_4^-]} = k_{\text{obs}} = k_c K_h K_a [\text{H}^+] [\text{RNH}_2] / ([\text{H}^+] + K_a)$$

$$\approx k_1 [\text{RNH}_2]_0 [\text{H}^+]^0 \quad \text{at higher } [\text{H}^+]$$

(Therefore [H⁺] >> K_a and periodate exist as HIO₄ in the higher acid medium employed)

The stoichiometry also further confirms the given mechanism as it shows almost 1 : 3 dependence of oxidant-to-substrate ratio including transfer of almost 9 electrons in three steps on an average of 3 electrons per substrate

The nitrene structure as the intermediate is a well-known feature in the oxidation of *N*-amino group. IR spectra of the product revealed peaks at 1330 (C–N) and 1429 cm⁻¹ (azo group attached to an aromatic electron-rich center). Further, the existence of the azo group was established from Raman spectral peak at 1580 cm⁻¹.

Experimental

5-Substituted-2-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazole : A mixture of carboxylic acid (0.01 mol), semicarbazide (0.01 mol) and H₂SO₄ (10 ml) was refluxed on a sand-bath for 2 h. It was then poured onto ice and neutralized with NH₄OH. The resulting solid was washed with double-distilled water, dried and crystallized from hot rectified spirit.

Kinetic measurements : The required molar concentration solution of the substrate was prepared in conductivity water. The oxidizing agents along with the requisite amount of supplement chemicals were taken separately and sufficient time was allowed to compensate for any change of heat during dilution. The two solutions were thermostated for at least 30–60 min before mixing. First 50 ml of oxidant solution, standardized just before mixing, was added with a standard rapid delivery pipette. The instant of mixing the reaction was followed by withdrawing 5 ml of aliquot of the reaction mixture at various intervals of time and the liberated iodine was titrated against standard thiosulfate solution to the conventional starch-iodine end-point. The esti-

mation of sodium periodate (NaIO_4) was made iodometrically in acid medium.

The kinetics were monitored by estimating iodometrically the disappearance of NaIO_4 at various time intervals. Both periodate solutions from the oxidant flask before mixing and the aliquote from the reaction mixtures at different time interval were analyzed. The pseudo first order rate constants, expressed as or k_{obs} (sec^{-1}) were calculated from the usual integrated expression.

Stoichiometry of the reaction was carried out by mixing large excess of the substrate concentration with the standard concentration of the oxidant (10 : 1 ratio) maintaining a constant temperature. The aliquots were taken at 1, 6, 24, 48 h intervals and titrated to find out the stoichiometry ratio of the oxidant with that of the substrate.

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